

REPAIR OF CF/PA6 LAMINATES BELOW MELTING POINT WITH BARELY VISIBLE IMPACT DAMAGE

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1 Introduction

The interlaminar toughness of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates is much lower than the in-plane toughness. For this reason, out-of-plane impact causes internal damages, such as delamination and transverse cracks [1]. Unfortunately, external impact damage, such as dents and fiber breakage, is sometimes too small to find, although internal damage is widespread in laminates. This type of problem is well known as barely visible impact damage (BVID) and results in a decrease in residual compressive strength. Thus, suppressing and repairing internal damage associated with BVID are important to improve the compression-after-impact (CAI) strength and damage tolerance of CFRP structures.

Since thermoplastics have high fracture toughness, the interlaminar toughness of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs) is much higher than that of CFRP using thermoset matrices [2]. They are therefore expected to suppress internal impact damage causing a decrease in residual compressive strength. Because of this advantage, CFRTPs have attracted attention for use in the primary structure of aircraft [3]. In addition, technology to reduce the ply thickness of CFRP has been developed [4, 5], markedly decreasing the amount of internal impact damage in thin-ply CFRTP laminates [6, 7]. On the other hand, thermoplastics are melted or softened by heating. Using these characteristics, it is possible to repair impact damage caused by the fracture and/or deformation of thermoplastics [6, 8, 9]. The repair technique is conducive to recovering the residual compressive strength of CFRTP laminates.

There are two types of impact damage excluding fiber breakage, which are caused by thermoplastic failure or deformation. Delamination and transverse cracks result from the former. Previous studies showed that delamination decreases the residual compressive strength because it leads to the local buckling of laminates [10]. Thus, thermal fusion bonding (TFB) is a key method used to repair the internal damage and recover the compressive strength. However, the authors' research for thin-ply CFRTP laminates has shown that the CAI strength was still lower than that of the intact specimen (Intact), even though the delamination area was small [7]. In this case, it was suggested that the reduction of strength was caused by out-of-plane deformation and/or residual stress, which led to the deformation. Since CFRTP laminates tend to have high interlaminar toughness and allow the propagation of little delamination, it is important to develop a method of repairing damage caused by dents, such as by flattening the deformation and/or relaxing the internal stress by annealing.

There are two important points regarding the repair of thermoplastic deformation as discussed above. One is to clarify the factor, i.e., out-of-plane deformation or residual stress, that governs CAI strength in the case that CFRTP laminates have a delamination length below the threshold defined in the following discussion. The other is to know the conditions of application of the repair method. Since large delamination causes local buckling, the compressive strength does not recover after repairing, and we should use TFB to repair the delamination. Suemasu investigated the relation between the local buckling load generated by the

damaged area and the global buckling load of CFRP laminates in terms of the length of internal damage in the longitudinal direction [10]; there were no dents on their model specimens. Their studies showed that local buckling occurred before global buckling when the delamination length in the laminates was sufficiently large. Thus, it is important to determine the threshold length of delamination causing local buckling if only a dent has been repaired.

In this study, specimens with different impact delamination area were repaired below the melting point to reduce the size of the dent. They were then compressed to experimentally determine the threshold delamination length causing local buckling. To reduce the residual stress caused by impact, annealing was also carried out for specimens with small impact damage. Here, the effect of reducing the residual stress on the compressive strength was evaluated.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials and Specimens

The specimens were made of TR50/polyamide 6 (PA6) unidirectional semi-prepreg supplied by Mituya Co., Ltd. The thickness and fiber volume fraction of the semi-prepreg were 0.043 mm and 54%, respectively.

In this study, we chose suitable molding conditions so that PA6 was completely impregnated into the fiber bundle and that no washout of the fibers and/or matrix occurred. Here, the melting point of PA6 is about 483 K. Two types of laminates were prepared for the tests, as shown in Table 1; these laminates are referred to as thin-ply laminates and thick-ply laminates, and their stacking sequences correspond to those in the authors' previous study [7]. These laminates were made of the same semi-prepreg plies. One lamina of a thick-ply laminate consisted of three plies oriented in the same direction. Thus, each lamina in the thick-ply laminates was three times thicker than in the thin-ply laminates, whereas the total thickness of the laminates was the same. The projected area of damage due to delamination in the thin-ply laminates was smaller than that in the thick-ply laminates under the same impact conditions in our preliminary study [7].

The thin-ply laminates were molded using a hot-press machine at a pressure of 2 MPa and a temperature of 553 K for 7200 s (= 2 h). After that, the laminates were slowly cooled for 21600 s (= 6 h) at the same pressure.

The molding conditions of thick-ply laminates were the same as those of the thin-ply laminates except for pressure; a pressure of 1 MPa was applied to the thick-ply laminates because fiber/matrix washout occurred at 2 MPa.

The specimen geometries were chosen so that global buckling of the intact specimen did not occur in the compression test discussed in section 2.5. The length (parallel to 0° direction), width (parallel to 90° direction), and thickness of all specimens subjected to the compression tests were about 120, 40, and 3 mm, respectively. Three specimens of each type of laminate were used in all tests.

2.2 Impact Tests

An impact load was applied to each specimen using a stainless-steel drop weight with a mass of 0.998 kg. The indenter used in the impact tests was 16 mm in diameter. A specimen was placed in a stainless-steel fixture, which had a cutout hole of 30 mm diameter at its center, as shown in Fig. 1. The impact energy applied to the specimen was selected to be 1.0 J/mm, because a small projected damage area due to delamination occurred at this impact energy for thin-ply and thick-ply laminates in a preliminary test. In addition, a test with an impact energy of 1.5J/mm was also carried out using Thick-ply laminates to evaluate the effect of a larger delamination area.

After impact, the amount of out-of-plane deformation (see Fig. 2) was measured. The delamination length in the longitudinal direction was also measured by ultrasonic inspection, as shown in Fig. 3. If the delamination length was larger than the gauge length of the stainless-steel fixture, as discussed in section 2.5, the delamination length was regarded as the gauge length (20 mm), because the compression of the delamination area by the fixture did not perfectly affect the buckling length.

2.3 Annealing and Repair of Impact Damage

Three types of repair process were carried out: 1) annealing, 2) repairing only the dent below the melting temperature, 3) repair by TFB above the melting point. In this study, annealing is also

considered as a repair process because we expected that the residual stress and dent deformation would partly recover. Here, the glass transition temperature, T_g , and melting point, T_m , of PA6 are about 333 and 483 K, respectively. The temperature used for the annealing test and the test which only the dent was repaired was set to between T_g and T_m .

In the annealing test, after being subjected to the impact test, specimens were heated at 373 K without the application of pressure, as shown in Table 1, and these conditions were maintained for 300 s (= 5 min). This temperature is between T_g and T_m of PA6, and was the minimum temperature at which the out-of-plane deformation was sufficiently flattened in the subsequent test in which only the dent was repaired. Then, the specimens were slowly cooled for 5400 s (= 1.5 h).

The pressure used to repair the dent was selected to be the same as that using during molding. In addition, the thermal history was the same as that of the annealing. After the impact test, specimens were pressed and heated at 373 K (see Table 1), and the conditions were maintained for 300 s (= 5 min). Then, the specimens were slowly cooled for 5400 s (= 1.5 h) at the same pressure.

In the case of repairing delamination and transverse cracks by TFB, the dent was first repaired by pressing the specimens under the same conditions as above. Then, the specimens were pressed at 2 MPa and 483 K after repairing the dent and the conditions were maintained for 900 s (= 15 min). After that, the specimens were slowly cooled at the same pressure.

After these annealing and repairing tests, the residual out-of-plane deformation and delamination in the specimens were measured again.

2.4 In situ Observation of Repair

We carried out in situ observation to investigate the change in internal damage during repair to check that the damage in the specimen was bonded under the thermal conditions used for repair by TFB (above 483 K), but not bonded in the case of annealing and repairing only the dent (373 K). In these tests, thick-ply laminates were used as the specimens. Since the projected damage area and crack opening displacement (COD) of the thick-ply laminates were larger than those of the thin-ply laminates [7], we expected to observe TFB behavior

of the COD caused by the delamination in the specimen.

After impact loading, specimens were cut out from the thick-ply laminates in the longitudinal direction to include the impact point and polished to observe the TFB behavior of internal damage. Then, each specimen was compressed in a thermostatic chamber and the behavior of the damage was observed using an optical microscope, as shown in Fig. 4. Here, the pressure was 2 MPa and the temperature of the chamber was increased slowly until the COD caused by delamination was zero. After the cracks were closed at the temperature, the specimen was polished again to determine whether or not the cracks had bonded.

2.5 Compression Tests

Compression tests were carried out using a servo-hydraulic testing machine (Shimadzu, 100 kN). Specimens were held in the loading fixture shown in Fig. 5. The result of CAI tests using this fixture approximately agrees with that of a full-scale experiment using SACMA SRM 2-88 [11, 12]. The crosshead speed was 0.01667 mm/s (= 1 mm/min). To measure the compressive strain and observe the buckling behavior, two strain gauges were attached on both sides of the specimen. The gauge length for all compression tests was 20 mm. It was confirmed that this length did not cause overall buckling in the intact specimen [7]. It is therefore considered that the buckling of the specimen led to impact damage. Here, specimens for compression tests after the annealing test, repair of only the dent, and repair by TFB were referred to as CAR_A, CAR_D, and CAR_TFB specimens in the following discussion, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 In situ Observation of Repair

Figs. 6a and 6b compare the same impact damage (delamination and a transverse crack) in the specimens with thick-ply laminates caused by an impact load before and after repair, respectively. Before repair, the COD of the delamination had certain positive value as indicated by the red dashed box. Under in situ observation, the COD of delamination suddenly became zero at the melting point of PA6. After polishing, the COD of the

delamination was still zero, although the specimen was not pressed, as shown in Fig. 6b. The transverse crack in the enlarged box in Fig. 6b was also closed. These closed cracks indicate that TFB occurred and that these cracks were bonded at the melting point. In short, the impact damage was repaired by TFB.

The internal damage was not repaired until the temperature exceeded the melting point of the thermoplastic resin. Thus, in the following discussion, we consider that the length of internal damage remains constant below the melting point during the repair process.

3.2 Impact Tests

Fig. 7 shows typical images obtained by ultrasonic inspection of a specimen with thin-ply laminates under an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm. We observed a small projected damage area and delamination length, as shown in Table 2.

Figs. 8a and 8b show typical delamination images observed by ultrasonic inspection for specimens with thick-ply laminates subjected to impact energies of 1.0 and 1.5 J/mm, respectively. The delamination length shown in Fig. 8b (1.5 J/mm) was clearly larger than that in Fig. 8a (1.0 J/mm). In addition, it was also larger than the gauge length in the compression test (20 mm).

While a large amount of scatter was observed for the delamination length of thin-ply laminates, that of thick-ply laminates was small relative to its average value. There was no fiber breakage on the surface of all specimens after impact. Thus, we omit the effect of fiber breakage in the following discussion.

3.3 Annealing

Table 2 shows the delamination length, out-of-plane deformation, and compressive strength of specimens with thin-ply laminates after annealing (see conditions for CAR_A test in Table 2). In the compressive tests, all specimens were broken without local buckling.

It is interesting to note that the out-of-plane deformation of the specimen decreased from 0.10 mm to 0.06 mm during annealing test, even though pressure was not applied. Softening of the thermoplastic polymer led to stress relaxation in the specimen. Since the plastic becomes soft, carbon fibers deformed by the out-of-plane deformation become straight again and the residual stress of the fibers and matrix is relaxed.

As shown in Table 2, the strength of CAR_A specimens with thin-ply laminates was about 2% lower than that of intact specimens with thin-ply laminates. It was also about 11% higher than that of CAI specimens with the thin-ply laminates after annealing, as referred to in section 3.6.

3.4 Repair of only Dent

Figs. 9a and 9b show the surface of a specimen with thick-ply laminates before and after repairing only the dent, respectively; the specimen was subjected to an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm. Before repairing only the dent, the average out-of-plane deformation of the specimen was about 0.12 mm, as shown in Table 2. After repair, the average amount of out-of-plane deformation was 0.02 mm. In the thin-ply and thick-ply laminates with an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm, the out-of-plane deformation was also decreased.

As shown in Table 2, the strength of the CAR_D specimens with thin-ply laminates was about 8% higher than that of the specimens with thick-ply laminates. This result is in agreement with the authors' previous study [7]. The compressive strength of the thick-ply specimens with an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm was about 9% lower than that of the specimens with an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm owing to the widespread delamination, as reported in section 3.2.

Fig. 10 shows typical stress-strain curves of a specimen with thick-ply laminates and an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm. In this study, the buckling stress was defined as the point at which the stress-strain curves bend in different directions as indicated by an arrow in Fig. 10. Buckling behavior was observed in all specimens with thick-ply laminates and an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm and the buckling stress was less than the compressive strength, as shown in Table 2. In contrast, specimens with thin-ply and Thick-ply laminates and an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm were broken without buckling or at the instant of the buckling.

3.5 Other Compressive Tests

Table 2 also shows the results of impact and compression tests for the Intact, CAI, and CAR_TFB specimens. The strength of CAI specimens was nearly 13% less than that of the intact specimens. On the other hand, that of the CAR_TFB specimens was recovered to the same

level as the intact specimens. Figs. 11a and 11b show the same specimen before and after TFB, respectively. The internal damage was completely repaired. The out-of-plane deformation of the dent was also completely repaired by the TFB process, as shown in Table 2. As a result, the compressive strength of the CAR_TFB specimens was recovered.

3.6 Effect of Residual Stress on Compressive Strength

As shown in Table 1, the difference between the CAI and CAR_A specimens with thin-ply laminates is whether or not the specimens were heated after the impact test. When the specimens were heated, stress relaxation occurred as discussed in section 3.3. In addition, the out-of-plane deformation of the CAR_A specimens was much smaller than that of the CAI specimens, whereas compressive strength of the CAR_A specimens was higher, as shown in Table 2. Thus, it is clear that reducing the out-of-plane deformation and/or residual stress recovers the compressive strength.

The out-of-plane deformation of CAR_D specimens with Thin-ply laminates was smaller than that of CAR_A specimens, as shown in Table 2. However, the strength of CAR_A specimens was almost the same as that of CAR_D specimens. Since both specimens were heated under the same conditions, an equal amount of residual stress was expected to be removed. Thus, in the case of a small delamination, it is suggested that the strength of the CAI specimens was reduced by the residual internal stress generated by the dent rather than the out-of-plane deformation caused by the dent.

3.7 Threshold of Delamination Length for Buckling of CAR_D Specimens

To experimentally confirm the existence of a threshold delamination length, thick-ply laminates with impact energies of 1.0 and 1.5 J/mm were prepared to change delamination length in CAR_D specimens. Fig. 12 shows the relation between the delamination length and buckling stress. The data points represent the results of a compression test for each CAR_D specimen with thick-ply laminates. The solid line represents the intact strength of thick-ply laminates. In this study, the number of data points may be too small, or the slope of the line may be too low to determine the threshold accurately.

The delamination length of the specimen with an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm was clearly larger than

that of the specimen with an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm, as reported in section 3.2. In addition, the buckling behavior was observed in the specimen with an impact energy of 1.5 J/mm before it broke. The buckling stress was lower than that of the Intact specimens.

Thus, the dashed line in Fig. 12 roughly indicates the relationship between the delamination length and buckling stress. The threshold delamination length can be determined as the intersection of the curve with the line for the intact specimen to be about 8.6 mm. This mechanism agrees with the result of a recent work by Suemasu [10]. Thus, the delamination length for which only the repair of the dent was sufficient below this threshold value.

3.8 Comparison of Annealing, Repair of only Dent, and TFB

In the thin-ply laminates, the strength of CAI specimens was about 13% less than that of the intact specimens. However, the strength of the CAR_TFB specimens was almost completely recovered to that of the intact specimens. It is interesting to note that the strength of CAR_A specimens was also recovered to 98% of that of the intact specimens, even though the internal damage in the specimens was not repaired. The strength of CAR_D specimens was also recovered to 96% of that of the intact specimens. Repairing only the dent below the melting point is a reasonably effective repair method to recover the compressive strength of the CFRTPL laminates with BVID.

Since the glass transition temperature is lower than the melting point, the method of repairing only the dent is easier than TFB, and the compressive strength after repair can be recovered more easily for CFRTPL laminates. In addition, it is useful to determine the application range of the method of repairing only dent using the threshold critical delamination length causing local buckling.

To establish the repair conditions for CFRTPL laminates, we should consider the following effects on compressive strength after repairing only the dent or by TFB as future works: 1) the effect of fiber breakage caused by impact, 2) determination of the threshold delamination length by numerical analysis and more accurate experiments, 3) quantitative evaluation of the relation between stress relaxation and the residual compressive strength of laminates after repair and/or annealing.

4 Conclusions

1. In thin-ply CF/PA6 laminates subjected to an impact energy of 1.0 J/mm, the strength of the CAI specimens was about 13% less than that of the intact specimens. Annealing at 373 K (below the melting point of PA6) recovered the compressive strength to 98% of that of the intact specimens in the case of a short length of delamination.
2. Repairing only the dent process below the melting point also recovered the compressive strength to 96% of that of the intact specimens in the case of a short length of delamination.
3. It was experimentally confirmed that a threshold delamination length causing buckling existed through compression tests with specimens with only the dent repaired.

Table 1 Relation between specimens subjected to compressive tests and impact/repair conditions.

Repair condition	Specimen name	Number of specimens		Conditions		
		Thin-ply [0/90] _{18s}	Thick-ply [0 ₃ /90 ₃] _{6s}	Impact energy [J/mm]	Temperature [K]	Repair Pressure [MPa]
Intact	Intact	3	3	-	-	-
Without repair	CAI	3	-	1.0	-	-
Annealing	CAR_A	3	-	1.0	373	-
Repair of only dent	CAR_D	3	3	1.0, 1.5*	373	2 (Thin-ply), 1 (Thick-ply)
TFB	CAR_TFB	3	-	1.0	483	2

$T_g = 333$ [K], $T_m = 483$ [K] *Thick-ply only

Table 2 Results of compressive tests and impact damage: delamination length and out-of-plane deformation.

Specimen name	Stacking sequence	Impact energy [J/mm]	Delamination length [mm]	Amount of out-of-plane deformation [mm]		Compressive strength [MPa]	Buckling stress [MPa]
				Before repair	After repair		
Intact	Thin-ply	-	-	-	-	524 (19)	-
	Thick-ply	-	-	-	-	460 (7.8)	-
CAI	Thin-ply	1.0	7.2 (6.6)	-	-	455 (34)	-
CAR_A	Thin-ply	1.0	2.3 (3.2)	0.10 (0.003)	0.06 (0.009)	514 (17)	-
CAR_D	Thin-ply	1.0	0.3 (0.5)	0.08 (0.008)	0.03 (0.006)	505 (51)	-
	Thick-ply	1.0	8.3 (0.4)	0.08 (0.012)	0.01 (0.007)	468 (12)	-
	Thick-ply	1.5	17.3 (4.6)	0.12 (0.012)	0.02 (0.009)	425 (34)	405 (22)
CAR_TFB	Thin-ply	1.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	535 (36)	-

Standard deviations are in parentheses.

Fig. 1. Schematic image of setup of impact test.

Fig. 2. Schematic image of amount of out-of-plane deformation.

Fig. 3. Schematic image of delamination length measured by ultrasonic inspection. When delamination occurred at more than one location, as shown in Fig. 3b, we regarded the distance between the ends of the delamination areas through the dent as the length of delamination.

Fig. 4. Setup of in situ observation test; CF/PA6 laminates heated in a thermostatic chamber were compressed by rods and the internal damage was observed using an optical microscope through the glass window of the chamber.

Fig. 5. Fixture used for compression test; a specimen was fixed and supported by stainless-steel blocks shown on the right of the photograph, and a compressive load was applied through the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen.

Fig. 6. TFB behavior of delamination and transverse crack in CF/PA6 laminates; photographs a and b represent before and after TFB, respectively.

Fig. 8. Images obtained by ultrasonic inspection of internal impact damage, shown as a bright (warm) color; Figs.8a and 8b show specimens with impact energies of 1.0 and 1.5 J/mm, respectively.

Fig. 7. Typical image obtained by ultrasonic inspection of internal damage, shown as a bright (warm) color and indicated by arrow, in Thin-ply specimen with impact energy of 1.0 J/mm.

Fig. 9. Repaired dent on specimen surface.

Fig. 11. Repair of internal impact damage by TFB; internal damage is shown as a bright (warm) color in Fig. 11a. The internal damage completely disappeared after repair by TFB, as shown in Fig. 11b.

Fig. 10. Typical stress-strain curves of CAR_D specimen; showing the buckling behavior of the specimen with impact energy of 1.5 J/mm before repairing only the dent.

Fig. 12. Relation between delamination length and compressive stress of Thick-ply laminates; solid and dashed lines represent the intact strength of the laminates and the curve fit to the data plots of compressive stress, respectively. The intersection of these lines was the experimental threshold delamination length for which repair of the only dent is sufficient.

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